

ARABIC LITERARY LANGUAGE AND DIALECTS

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Annotation:

This article explores the distinction between Classical Arabic (Fusha) and the various Arabic dialects, challenging the misconception that ancient Arab tribes spoke in the same standardized form of Arabic used in modern media and official contexts. The article emphasizes that the diversity of Arabic dialects is deeply rooted in the geographical and ethnic dispersion of tribes across the Arabian Peninsula and the influence of historical and colonial factors.

Key terms: Historical Dialect Diversity, **Colonialism**, the spread of Islam and the influence of Western colonialism, linguistic variations, modern dialects, **Dialect**, **Fusha Debate**.

Introduction

If you think that the ancient Arab tribes also spoke in today's Fusha Arabic (Literary Arabic language) used in historical national TV series and official communication, you would be wrong. Because among the ancient Arab tribes, there were many dialects (Arabic language dialects) like today. The multiplicity of dialects of the Arabic language is explained by the fact that the tribes are ethnically and geographically dispersed throughout the Arabian Peninsula. Also, the spread of Islam among all tribes, more precisely throughout Arabia, served as an important factor in this regard. Also, the inhabitants of the Arabic-speaking countries, such as Algeria, Tunisia, and Morocco, which were colonies of Western colonialists, were also influenced by the foreign language. The different Arabic dialects of the past differed sharply in terms of pronunciation and speech, just as they do today.

Data Collection And Analysis

Today's dialects, which have been formed in a variety of ways, are actually a part of the ancient Arab tribes, which have been passed down from generation to generation. It is known that the Arabic language differs from other languages with its complex grammar, morphological semantics, structural structure of sentences, complex terms that acquire deep and diverse meanings. Now, if we add the issue of Arabic dialects to these features, it is natural that this situation will cause a lot of difficulties for the language learner. In addition, in almost all Arab countries, a large segment of the population, especially the youth mass, communicates in full dialects today. That is why Arabic fusha or Arabic dialects as a means of daily communication has always been a subject of intense debate among Arabic linguists, intellectuals, poets and thinkers. Some thinkers call this process "الفصحى بَيْنَ الصِّراغِ" "العَامِيَّةِ و" that is, "struggle between literature and dialect".¹

At the beginning of the 20th century, Mustafa Sadiq al-Rafi'i, who is known as one of the most prominent defenders of the Arabic language field, has fierce debates with the opposition on the same issue.

His opinion was opposed by several scholars such as Ahmad Lutfi Sayyed, the chairman of the Arabic Language Association in Cairo. Several articles by Ahmed Lutfi were published in the Egyptian newspaper "al-Jariydah" on the same issue. He writes his work "tamsirul lug'ah" i.e. "mastering the language" dedicated to this issue. According to him, the Arabic language should be completely separated from the language of the Arab nation. He also proposes to introduce new foreign words such as "aftomobil, bantaluvn, jiket, beskelet" in Arabic.

The famous writer Salama Musa was one of his ideological followers. He said that "Fusha should be completely abandoned and the dialect language should be introduced as the official language of the Arab countries instead. Because the Fusha

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language is very difficult and at the same time it cannot meet the requirements of the development of the new culture of the Arab lands.

The famous writer Toha Husayn was against them. He said that "of course, the Arab Fusha is the basis of the idea of uniting the entire Arab nation. Because if you write in Fusha, you will be understood well by all Arabs, from the Arab sea to the ocean. Bordiyu, if you write in Egyptian dialect, only Egyptians will understand you. "From the past until now, there has been sympathy for Fusha and negative opinions about the dialect," he says.

Result and Discussion

If we look at the reality, it is observed that some intellectuals speak in dialects in their performances in mass media, in the fields of national cinematography, science and culture. When you hear some dialects, you think they are speaking a language other than Arabic. We would not be wrong if we say that these issues are one of the global problems facing Arabic linguistics today. True, the formation of dialects does not require specific grammatical rules. All the rules are basically necessary for the Fusha language. That is why it is necessary for a person who starts to learn Arabic to learn it in Fusada. In addition, if those who are interested in the Arabic language have information about the Arabic dialects, their language learning process will be easier. Because according to our observations, the change and other processes in Arabic dialects are not a process to be learned, but to be understood. Therefore, language learners or researchers must first distinguish between Fusha and dialect.

We have decided to cover some of the Arabic dialects below in order to serve as a small guide for new researchers and students.

Kakasha dialect: at the time when we end the word by endowment, it is muhotab kaf, i.e. 2nd person singular, reading by changing the kaf letter "k" to the letter shin. This dialect was the communication language of Muzarr, , Rabi'a, Bakr and some Tamim and Asad tribes at that time. The same process can be found in the language

of Majnun in the famous work "Layli and Majnun":

"فَعَيْنَاهُ و جِيدُهَا و جِيدُهَا"

ولا كَنَّ عَظْمُ السَّاقِ مِثْلَ دَقِيقٍ"

“Your eye is his eye, and your neck is his neck.

But the bone of your calf is thin.”

In this ode from the tongue of Majnun, the letters under the yellow color were actually the 2nd person singular kaf letter " ك " .

Al-istinto dialect: this dialect was the communication language of Sa'd ibn Bakr and the communication dialect of the tribes of Hudayl, Azd, Qays, and Ansar. In this dialect, the letter “ ط ” next to the silent letter a'yn is changed to the letter “ ن ”.

For example:

أعط - أنط

إنا أعطيناك الكوثر - إنا أنطيناك الكوثر

This change is even one of the recitations of the Holy Qur'an. Today, the same dialect can be found among some Arab tribes of Iraq.

Al-Wahm Dialect: This dialect was the communication language of the Rabi'a and to a limited extent the Bani Kalb tribes. In the Mazukr dialect, the vowel before the hoyi havas letter is changed to a kasha.

"منهم، عنهم" - "منهم، عنهم"

Al-'an 'ana dialect: This dialect was the language of many tribes, especially the Qays and Tamiim tribes. In this dialect, the letter hamza is changed to ayn. For example:

"أنتك - عنك" "أسلم - عسلم" "أذن - عذن"

"أشهد أنك رسول الله - أشهد عنك رسول الله"

"May God bless you - May God bless you"

Kota dialect: This dialect is the language of the Tai tribe, in which the last letter of the word is cut off and left unpronounced. This is similar to the rule of translation

in the science of Tajweed. According to lexicographers, the same dialect can be found among Egyptian Arabs. For example:

"يا ولد- يا ول ، يا غُلام – يا غلا ، مساء الخير – سَلْ خير "

However, among these tribes, the Quraysh tribe, unlike other tribes, used to communicate in pure Arabic literary language without all the dialects mentioned above. The following interesting incident caught our attention. According to the story, Khalid ibn Safwan ibn Ibrahim al-Tamiimi Muzari and the famous scholar Mahramata ibn Kindi Yamani were sitting in the presence of Caliph Abul Abbas. Then the following interesting conversation took place between two mature scholars.

Muzori asked Kindiy:

- "-Were you the greatest lexicographer of your people? Yes it is.
- What does the eye say? He calls the eye "jahma".
- What does Tishni say? Tishni is called "mezam".
- What does the ear say? He calls the ear "sonnoroh".
- What about the fingers? He calls his fingers "shanotir".
- What is the wolf's name? It is called "quto".

Then Muzari replied to him:

"إنَّا أنزلناه قرءانا عربيا لعَلَّكُمْ تَعْقِلُونَ"، "Allah Almighty says in the Holy Qur'an:

"We sent it down as an Arabic Qur'an, so that you may use your intellect." (Yusuf-2) Or:

"بِلِسَانٍ عَرَبِيٍّ مُبِينٍ"

"(Revealed) in plain Arabic" (Shuaro-195)

"وَمَا أَرْسَلْنَا مِنْ رَسُولٍ إِلَّا بِلِسَانِ قَوْمِهِ"

"When We sent any Messenger, We sent them in the language of their people." (Ibrahim-4)

states that So we are Arabs. "The Qur'an was revealed in our language. Don't you see? Allah the Exalted said: {الْعَيْنِ بِالْعَيْنِ} But he did not say {الْجَهْمُ بِالْجَهْمِ} And

he said {الْمَيِّزُ بِالْمُرْنِ} But he did not say: ” {الْسِّنُّ بِالْسِّنِّ} And he said, "Wal uzunu bil uzuni." {الْأُذُنُ بِالْأُذُنِ} But al-Sonnarotu bis sannaroti did not say , {السَّنَارَةُ بِالْسَّنَارَةِ} And he said "yaj'aluvna asobia'hum fiy azanihim", {يَجْعَلُونَ أَصَاعَهُمْ فِي آذَانِهِمْ} However, he did not say "shanatirohum fi sonnarotihim" {فَأَكَلَهُ الذَّنْبُ} He also said "faakalahuz zibu" {فَأَكَلَهُ الكُتْعُ} But he didn't say "faakalakhul kuta" {فَأَكَلَهُ الكُتْعُ} protested.

From the heated debate between these two scholars, we understand that the difference between the Arabic dialects and the holy verses of the Qur'an is significantly different. That is why the topic of Arabic languages and dialects is as diverse and endless as the ocean. With the above thoughts, we are far from the conclusions that "dialects are not Arabic, they are not needed" or "it is not necessary to learn fusha".

Therefore, many dialects such as Ana'na, Kashkasha, are a manifestation of the dialects of the old Arabic language, their national heritage passed from generation to generation. But even if we take it at the scale of the entire region, the only basis that preserves the Arabic language, its purity, and preserves it from changes and the influence of other languages is precisely the classical Arabic literature and the literary Arabic language itself.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the exploration of Arabic literary language (Fusha) and its dialects reveals a complex and rich linguistic landscape shaped by historical, geographical, and cultural forces. The ancient Arab tribes did not speak the standardized form of Arabic we recognize today in historical dramas and official communications. Instead, they used a variety of dialects, each influenced by the tribal, ethnic, and geographical diversity of the Arabian Peninsula. This historical multiplicity continues to influence modern Arabic dialects, which have also been shaped by colonialism and the spread of Islam.

The debate over the role of Fusha versus dialects highlights the ongoing tension between linguistic tradition and modern communication needs. Scholars like Mustafa Sadiq al-Rafi'i, Ahmad Lutfi Sayyed, and Salama Musa have contributed significantly to this discourse, offering differing perspectives on whether Fusha should remain central or if dialects should take precedence in contemporary contexts. Taha Hussein's argument for the unifying role of Fusha underscores its importance in fostering a shared Arab identity across diverse regions. Thus, while dialects offer valuable insights into the evolution of Arabic and enrich our understanding of its history, Fusha remains an essential cornerstone for preserving the language's purity and literary tradition. The interaction between dialects and Fusha exemplifies the dynamic and evolving nature of Arabic, highlighting the importance of both in the linguistic and cultural fabric of the Arab world.

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